

CULTIVATE

Food Sharing Governance Landscape Comparison of the CULTIVATE hub locations: Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Brief Methodological Note	5
3. Comparing Enablers and Barriers for the FSIs in Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan. 12	12
3.1 Food Waste Recovery and Redistribution	12
3.1.1 Structural Factors, Local Conditions and Discourses	12
3.1.2 Regulatory and Policy Frameworks.....	12
3.1.3 Resources and Knowledge	13
3.1.3.1 Funding schemes.....	13
3.1.3.2 Spaces and procuring food.....	13
3.2.3.3 Technical Knowledge and Skills.....	14
3.1.4 Participation, Internal Organisation and Networks	14
3.1.4.1 Volunteers and Internal Dynamics.....	14
3.1.4.2 Networks and Conflicts among Actors.....	15
3.2 Community-based Urban Agriculture	16
3.2.1 Structural Factors, Local Conditions and Discourses	16
3.2.2 Regulatory and Policy Frameworks.....	16
3.2.3 Resources and Knowledge	18
3.2.3.1 Funding schemes.....	18
3.2.3.2 Spaces, Soil Conditions and Other Resources.....	18
3.2.3.3 Technical Knowledge and Skills.....	18
3.2.4 Participation and Internal Organisation.....	19
3.2.4.1 Volunteering, Individual Culture and Possible Conflicts.....	19
3.2.4.2 Networks and Conflicts among Actors.....	19
4. Recommendations Emerged in the Three City Hubs	21
4.1 Food Recovery and Redistribution.....	21
4.1.1 For Administrations and Policymakers	21
4.1.2 For Food Sharing Initiatives	21
4.1.3 For the Private Sector	21
4.2 Food Sharing Gardens and Urban Agriculture	26
4.2.1 For Administrations and Policymakers	26
4.2.2 For Food Sharing Initiatives	26

4.2.3 For the Private Sector27

5. Conclusions 31

6. References 33

1. Introduction

This report provides a comparative analysis of three food sharing governance landscape studies conducted in the three hub cities of the European Project CULTIVATE. The reports of the governance landscapes of Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) of Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan analyse how initiatives for food waste recovery and redistribution (FWR), Community-Based Urban Agriculture (CBUA), and Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) unfold in specific governance and socio-ecological contexts. The study of these three food-sharing sectors in the three cities has included exploring the socio-cultural and environmental conditions, the policy and regulatory frameworks, and the sectoral governance food sharing dynamics in each place. The analysis of secondary data and interviews with key stakeholders from the FSIs and the public and private sectors has resulted in the identification of enablers and barriers for enhancing the sustainability impact of food sharing initiatives as well as developing policy recommendations for the different sectors, actors and cities. The research conducted in the three cities followed a common protocol which allowed the comparison of the three governance landscapes, identifying similarities and differences among the three cities. In particular, the comparison of the enablers and barriers, as well as the recommendations, offers a deeper understanding of the dynamics, challenges, and opportunities of the FSIs, which can be shared with other cities across Europe.

The remainder of the report is organised as follows. First, a Brief Methodology Note in Chapter 2 describes the research questions and key methodological considerations. Chapter 3 analyses barriers and enablers for the FWR and CBUA initiatives, and Chapter 4 investigates the Recommendations suggested. Finally, the Conclusions in Chapter 5 summarise key insights highlighting similarities and differences among the FSIs governance landscape of Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan.

2. Brief Methodological Note

This comparative analysis builds on the study of the food sharing governance landscapes of Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan. The methodology used for this multicity study is based in a common research protocol which includes using a mixture of methods and data sources. In each city, three food sharing sectors are analysed, namely Food Waste Recovery and Redistribution (FWR), Community-Based Urban Agriculture (CUBA), and Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE). The reports depict the socio-cultural contexts of food sharing, analyse official reports, regulatory frameworks, policies and strategic plans; and identify key projects and food sharing initiatives (FSIs) in each city. Additionally, primary data collected allowed us to further understand how key local actors from the public, private sector, and FSIs perceive the incumbent food sharing governance landscape (BCN 1; UTH 1; MIL 1). A key result of the analysis is the identification of place-based barriers and enablers to sustainable food sharing for each city, as well as the development of recommendations to overcome barriers directed towards the public and private sectors and for the FSIs.

Building on these city-based analysis, in this report we conduct a comparative study that highlights divergences and similarities among the governance landscapes of Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan and allows us to identify common and place-based difficulties and opportunities. Although the governance landscape reports follow a standard protocol, the comparison of the SSE has been excluded due to the divergent understandings of what is social and solidarity economy in each city and for local actors (see individual reports) and therefore what types of FSIs are part of this categorisation (from food banks to cooperatives). The comparative study thus focuses in community-based urban agriculture and food waste recovery and redistribution governance landscapes.

To perform this comparison, three research questions are addressed:

- What are the common barriers or enablers that FSIs deal with in the three cities? And which are the specific ones for each city?
- What are the common and specific recommendations to FSIs and the private and public sectors?
- Are there shared socio-demographic and structural factors that can influence the activities of FSIs?

First, the comparison of the enablers and barriers has been performed according to the tree code developed for the individual city governance landscape analysis. This tree code presented in Table 1, which is structured in nine dimensions and 67 subdimensions. The codification process was based on a tree code category developed from a systematic literature review of academic articles focused on governance and food sharing. An initial tree code was developed and later discussed through a participative process with CULTIVATE partners, a total of 48 participants representing academia, policymakers and food sharing initiatives across Europe. The tree code aimed to identify potential barriers and enablers using two levels of categories. The first level listed eight broad categories of barriers and enablers: actors' discourses, internal organisation, knowledge, participation, regulations, relations between actors, resources, and structural factors. Each category contained a second level of codes representing the most relevant aspects of the first-level categories. We

complemented the tree code during the process of analysis of the documents and interviews. The nine dimensions are clustered around the following areas:

- **Structural Factors, Local Conditions and Discourses** to deepen the political, economic, social, cultural, and environmental context conditioning FSI activities and organisations, and the arguments, opinions and statements related to them;
- **Regulatory and Policy Frameworks** that can limit, control, or encourage FSI-related activities.
- **Resources and Knowledge** to understand the channels available for the FSIs, such as funds, infrastructure, food, spaces, paid human resources, common/public resources, as well as technological and bureaucratic skills and tools, and;
- **Participation, Internal Organisation and Networks** to assess the interactions between FSIs and among different stakeholders that can shape and influence FSI practices, activities, actors, and issues.

Second, we conducted a comparison of the policy recommendations addressed to the FSIs and the public and private sectors, to reveal divergences and similarities among the three hub cities. This analysis showcases the role these actors can play in improving community-based agriculture and food waste recovery and redistribution initiatives. Place-based and general recommendations were also discussed with the other members and partners of Cultivate during the General Assembly in Utrecht on the 15th and 16th of May 2024 and complemented the analysis.

Finally, the comparison considers the diverse socio-ecological contexts, including demographic structure of the three cities, which inevitably influences their governance landscapes. For instance, Milan and Barcelona, with 1,4 and 1,8 million inhabitants, respectively, are similar in population and considered major European cities. In contrast, Utrecht, with a population 367.000, is a medium-sized city. Similarly, the geographical and environmental aspects reveal different conditions that have been deepened during the comparative analysis.

BARRIERS AND ENABLERS OF FOOD SHARING GOVERNANCE

CATEGORY LEVEL 1	DESCRIPTION	EXAMPLES OF CATEGORY LEVEL 2	DESCRIPTION
1. Structural factors	Aspects of the political, economic, social, cultural, and environmental context that condition FSI activities and organisations	External crises	Experiencing and being impacted by an external Crisis (e.g covid-19)
		Economy	Economic situation in the country/world shaping the local context
		Food culture	Local/regional production with pride in food culture/traditions as well as food waste cultures
		Political	Political elements shaping the local context (e.g., elections period, institutional jurisdiction, etc).
		Ecological	Ecological elements shaping the local context (e.g., great availability of water or water-use banned in city gardens due to climate-related drought).
2. Regulation	Laws, rules, or other orders or incentives prescribed or granted by an external authority, specifically to limit, control, or encourage FSI activities.	Food safety	food safety regulation, risk governance and liability rules (e.g FSI or food donor liability regarding the food safety of donated food)
		Food waste	Food waste regulation
		Free trade	Free trade policies dominating food policies (e.g., policies favouring commercial developments in empty plots)
		Urban Planning	Support, protection or promotion of FSI (especially urban gardens) through land use planning strategies
		Grants	Allocating public money to FSI initiatives. Linked to funding.
		Punitive actions	Fines on FSI practices (e.g., dumpster diving or gleaning)
		Integration	Integration of FS activities into urban food policies
		Policy coherence	Connecting food policies to other agendas (e.g., sustainability, climate, health)
		Bureaucracy	Bureaucratic processes
		Temporality	Temporary public leases for gardens, kitchens, etc.
3. Resources	Finance, infrastructure, food (regarding, for instance, quality, quantity)	Funding	Access to financial resources
		Infrastructure	Spaces, infrastructure, and equipment to operate (e.g., storage facilities, kitchens, land, etc) which

	or sustained access), paid human resources, common/public resources, technologies, tools and skills, etc.		can be temporal or stable and can be from FSI, public administration or business.
		Staff	Paid people who work for the organisation
		Volunteers	People who occasionally will help with carrying out the activities
		Self-exploitation	The act of exploiting oneself for the collective's gain. (which might be necessary to develop the project) - linked to burn-out code.
		Technical advice	Technical advice from professionals (e.g., accountant, technician...) which can be paid or non-paid.
		Institutional support	Support and recognition from public institutions
		ICT	Information and Communications Technology (ICT) tools
		Regulatory skills	Skills to navigate regulations to identify issues and opportunities.
		Food quality	Nutritional value or low food quality of the users' food parcels
		Food accessibility	Fair and organic food made accessible for all.
		Stability	Permanent premises (e.g due to leases or funders from public or private actors) and thus affecting the resources available.
		Water	Water limitations for growing food
		Soil	Quality of soil for growing food
4. Discourses	Arguments, opinions and statements related to FSI activities that are represented as facts ('truths') supported by definitions and theories	Commodity	Food as commodity
		Right	Food as a right
		Community-building	Food as a community-building activity
		Commons	Food as commons
		Health	FSI as contributing to people's good health (physical or mental)
		Climate	FSI as a way to address climate challenges, impact of climate on FSI

		Social movements perception	Role of social movements on providing solutions to local problems
		Public sector perception	Role of public sector on providing solutions to local problems
		Private sector perception	Role of private sector on providing solutions to local problems
		Recognition of benefits	Recognition and visibility of the social, economic, environmental and health-related benefits of FS activities
		Opposition	Discourses of local opposition (e.g due to conceptions of rescued food as dubious, or neighbours criminalising practices such dumpster diving or gleaning)
5. Relations (including power relations) between social actors	Modalities of interactions that can shape and influence FSI practices, activities, actors, and issues	Cooperation	Coordinated networks of external collaborators and allies.
		Capacity to influence	Influencing, participating and being included in diverse social processes (coalitions, networks, multi-stakeholder projects, policy processes, etc)
		Opposition	Experiencing opposition (e.g due to conceptions of rescued food as dubious)
		Competition	Conflicts related to competition between spaces in a city (e.g new surplus cafés relations with already existing cafes)
		External damages	External damages: vandalism, dogs, litter
6. Participation	A range of processes and issues through which the communities of FSI are involved and play a role in issues that affect them	Level of participation/commitment	Commitment and participation from the people involved in the FSI, in terms of counting with enough staff or people to fulfill the different roles needed to develop the project
		Burn-out	To become completely exhausted through overwork as a consequence of time-consuming tasks or even self-exploitation within a FSI
		Community-building activities	Organising community-building activities that bring the FSI group together (e.g dinners, recipe exchange, working sessions to repair infrastructure, etc.)
		Co-design	Co-design sessions with users (shared ownership)
		Vulnerable groups	Exclusion/Fragmentation of vulnerable groups

		Social stigma	Social stigma experienced by users when receiving food donations.
		Users' needs and perceptions	Complexity of including users perceptions & needs (i.e religious, cultural, taste) in food parcels or meals
		Donors' needs and perception	Donors' needs and perception (e.g about complexity of donating food)
7. Knowledge	Awareness, understanding, or information on FSI-related issues that has been obtained by experience or study	Technical	Technical and scientific knowledge (e.g knowing how to fundraise, admin skills, etc)
		Creativity/Innovation	Space for creativity and innovation - to think/act differently outside the box
		Lived experience	On the ground know how
8. Internal organization	Elements of the particular manner that FSI organise themselves to achieve their goals	Vision & Leadership	Project with a grand and defined idea of where the project is going and leadership (often shared among different people and roles).
		Adaptative capacity	Organisational flexibility, and being able to function with varying amount of money, resources, volunteers, etc. (e.g., changes of food surplus in food redistribution initiatives)
		Organisation environment	Environment for staff and volunteers in an organisation
		Quick decisions	Capacity to quickly respond to challenges and make decisions.
		Continuity	Lack of continuity/mechanisms of knowledge & skill transfer (e.g., if the main person leaves, who/how will be the knowledge transferred).
		Regeneration	Capacity to attract new members
9. Social actors	Relevant individuals, organisations, or institutions who play a part in FSI activities or in a FSI-related political scenario	Private sector	Individuals or organisations in economic and social life which are not controlled by the government and usually act for profit.
		Public sector	Public organizations that are subject to political rather than market control and whose objectives, structures, and processes are often set by legislation or bureaucratic agencies.
		Academia	Individual or collective members of a university or college who teach or do research (e.g., institutes, departments, etc).

		Civil society	Non-profit, citizens' groups that are organised on a local, national, or international level.
		FSI	Food sharing initiatives - initiatives explicitly set up to share food.
		Media	Organisations that control the main channels of mass communication (e.g., TV, newspapers, magazines, etc).

Table 1 - Tree code for the enablers and barriers analysis.

3. Comparing Enablers and Barriers for the FSIs in Barcelona, Utrecht and Milan

3.1 Food Waste Recovery and Redistribution

3.1.1 Structural Factors, Local Conditions and Discourses

The analysis of the sociocultural background of the three hub cities can stimulate, in different ways, the development and improvement of initiatives devoted to food waste recovery and redistribution. The sector has been consolidating in the last decade, and there is a shared awareness of the cultural value of the right to food and hospitality (BCN 3.4.1.1; UTH 4.3.1; MIL 3.6.1). Barcelona is a city where cooperativism and self-organisation thrive. (BCN 3.4.1.4). In Milan, historical initiatives devoted to hospitality and food redistribution grew particularly since the first half of the XIX century partly due to arrival of low-income groups to the city (MIL 3.11). In Utrecht, initiatives can rely on solid citizens' participation and a shared awareness of volunteering (UTH 4.3.1). A further structural enabler recognised in Milan – and considered valid in the other two cities – is the presence of a dense urban fabric that offers favourable conditions for micro-actions, optimising logistics, and strengthening relationships (MIL 3.6.3).

Moreover, food waste recovery and redistribution have been gaining ground as priorities in public and political agendas everywhere, especially after the COVID-19 emergency that highlighted how access to food is can be jeopardised and plays a crucial role in building solid communities in urban areas (BCN 3.4.1.1; UTH 4.3.1; MIL 3.4, 3.8). The right for everyone to access sustainable and healthy food and the environmental benefits of food waste recovery are now widely recognised. (BCN 3.4.1.6, 3.4.1.8; UTH 4.2.1; MIL 3.4). However, social stigma carried by needing and accepting recovered food is still reported as a crucial barrier in every hub city. Also, interviewees from Barcelona underline the charity perspective of the food basket distribution (BCN 3.4.2.3). This perception is also shared by informants of Milan and Utrecht, where initiatives are trying to address stigmatisation by opening shops based on a points system where users can purchase goods based on their needs and preferences – the aim is to switch the users's role from receivers of food aid to customers (MIL 3.4; UTH 4.4.8). Some limitations reported also include how to better integrate in initiatives people from different backgrounds, facing among other language barriers (BCN 3.4.2.6).

3.1.2 Regulatory and Policy Frameworks

The current regulatory and policy frameworks and programmes are mainly reported as enablers in Milan and Barcelona – they provide funds, resources, and protocols for procuring food. The Urban Food Policy of Milan provides a shared vision and plays a crucial role in organising different actors and building constructive networks. In addition, the national Italian law on food waste recovery defines precise rules for these initiatives (MIL 3.6.2). Similarly, interviewees from Barcelona recognise the same fundamental role of the regional food waste prevention law (BCN 3.4.1.7). However, bureaucracy, especially for managing and applying for funds, is considered as a barrier in both cities (BCN 3.4.2.7; MIL 3.7.3). In the Netherlands, food waste recovery is regulated at the national level only, and Utrecht's municipal policies and strategies are fragmented. Each

department (e.g. Societal Development, Work and Income, Spatial Development) developed independent policies and strategies that impact on different areas of the food system, resulting in a low coherence and integration between them. Different departments work together and in partnership with initiatives only through specific projects (UTH 4.2.3.5, 4.4.2). In this governance landscape, FSIs need to navigate across different policy domains and bureaucratic processes, resulting in cumbersome interpretation and application, resulting in additional skills and support needed (UTH 4.4.2).

The analysis of the policy and regulatory frameworks and the interviews have revealed that guaranteeing food safety is a crucial aspect that FWR initiatives must deal with. The national laws make FSIs responsible for the quality of food they distribute. In the three cities, regulatory frameworks on food safety and redistribution are sometimes challenging to interpret and apply, which limits surplus recovery. Informants from Barcelona report that the regulations concerning food safety are occasionally unclear and complicated to apply (BCN 3.4.2.8). In Milan, restrictions on household food recovery are viewed as legislative barriers that hinder efforts to increase food recovery and reduce waste (MIL 3.7.6). In Utrecht, food safety national regulations appear stricter than in the other cities; the leniency of inspections partially enables dumpster diving, gleaning and cooking with food waste (UTH 4.3.4). Moreover, the regulations on expiration dates are unclear for initiatives, leading to uncertainties about the quality of recovered food. Consequently, some edible food is wasted due to confusion about its safety (UTH 4.4.1).

3.1.3 Resources and Knowledge

3.1.3.1 Funding schemes

Thanks to the increasing public acceptance and commitment to deal with food waste, the three hub cities have seen an increase in funds for the initiatives devoted to food waste recovery and redistribution from the European, National, and regional programmes and private entities such as bank foundations (BCN 3.4.5; MIL 3.6.4; UTH 4.3.5). A municipal funding programme is reported only in Utrecht, which is, nonetheless, addressed to all volunteering initiatives (UTH 4.2.3.6). Although there is an increase in funding, FSIs in the three hub cities report a lack of sufficient funding, which is related to the significant financial efforts these initiatives have to face for logistics, train employees, and storage (BCN 3.4.2.1; UTH 4.4.3; MIL 3.7.5). Moreover, Milan reports that maintaining the food collection and distribution system in an environmentally and socially sustainable manner involves additional costs and resources (MIL 3.7.8). As previously mentioned (3.1.2), access to funds is limited by bureaucracy and the complexity of application processes.

3.1.3.2 Spaces and procuring food

Concerning space access and availability, Barcelona and Utrecht report a lack of infrastructure to meet logistics and storage needs for guaranteeing quality and safety standards for food surplus. In particular, initiatives from Barcelona defined the obstacles to access infrastructure as chronic (BCN 3.2.5; UTH 4.4.3). To overcome this deficit, initiatives in Utrecht can rely on neighbourhood community centres and connections to other actors of the local social and solidarity economy (UTH 4.3.2). In contrast, Milan has created food hubs on public premises, which offer FWR initiatives adequate spaces for their activities (e.g., food storage, distribution, and processing). In addition, the

administration has enabled collaborations with private actors that also offer their premises to FWR initiatives (MIL 3.2.2, 3.6.2).

The procurement of food is crucial for FWR initiatives, which rely on donations and their relationships with public and private actors. Food donations from European and National programmes (e.g. FEAD) contribute significantly to these FSIs. Still, donations from private and public companies (e.g., grocery shops, supermarkets, catering services and school canteens) also play a crucial role. Indeed, the first barrier identified in the three hubs is the progressive decrease of food surplus, which results from the combination of the changes in private companies and citizens' behaviours. Supermarkets, local shops, and canteens have been reducing surplus by improving their procedures to contrast food waste. The appearance of ICT private companies devoted to contrasting food waste, such as Too Good To Go and Last-Minute Market, has also reduced the surplus generated by small and large shops. In addition, there is a general change in food consumption, which is more attentive to have a lower environmental impact and to reduce food waste. Moreover, the food surplus of private and public companies fluctuates in quality and quantity, causing difficulties in providing healthy food and sometimes a mismatch between availability and demand (BCN 3.4.2.4; UTH 4.4.5, 4.4.6, 4.4.7; MIL 3.7.4, 3.8).

3.2.3.3 Technical Knowledge and Skills

In all three hubs, interviewees emphasized that the shortage of trained volunteers and staff poses a significant barrier in terms of technical knowledge and skills. The lack of expertise in navigating bureaucratic procedures for fund applications and compliance with regulatory frameworks is particularly noted (BCN 3.4.2.2; UTH 4.4.1, 4.4.2; MIL 3.7.7). In Milan, established organizations are making efforts to attract know-how by engaging retired professionals and managers from private food companies, while the Urban Food Policy Office offers general technical support to the hubs (MIL 3.7.7). In contrast, Barcelona and Utrecht primarily rely on a small group of dedicated volunteers who have gained experience within the organization over the years (BCN 3.4.2.2; UTH 4.3.1, 4.4.4). Across the three cities, the sector's growth and development have brought to light the need for "professionalized volunteers" capable of managing the increasing demand from those in need and ensuring compliance with regulations and fund applications (BCN 3.4.1.2; UTH 4.3.1; MIL 3.6.4).

3.1.4 Participation, Internal Organisation and Networks

3.1.4.1 Volunteers and Internal Dynamics

Interviewees from Utrecht recognise high participation in these initiatives, which can rely on passionate and stable volunteers and sporadic participants (UTH 4.3.1). In contrast, Milan and Barcelona report a shortage of stable volunteers, which represents a crucial barrier to the initiatives. Some Barcelona interviewees identify political polarisation of people and initiatives as a potential barrier that sometimes limits the participation of individuals who are not involved in such dynamics but are willing to collaborate (BCN 4.4.2.11). In Milan, the initiatives recognise difficulties in attracting stable and new volunteers (MIL 3.7.7). In the three cities, most volunteers are retired citizens with time to dedicate to the initiatives, while younger volunteers tend to participate sporadically (BCN 3.4.2.11; MIL 3.7.7). Despite the high participation, Utrecht also reports that 80% of volunteers are above 60, which can limit attracting new volunteers (UTH 4.4.4).

Concerning internal organisation, interviewees from the three hubs agree that there are difficulties in finding volunteers who participate regularly and that the most passionate volunteers play a crucial role in the success of the initiatives. However, while these members provide stability and continuity, they can also lead to internal conflicts due to varying levels of commitment among participants (BCN 3.4.1.2, 3.4.2.11; UTH 4.3.1, 4.4.4; MIL 3.7.7). Barcelona specifically mentions that non-formal initiatives are more susceptible to these internal conflicts (BCN 3.4.2.12).

3.1.4.2 Networks and Conflicts among Actors

In Barcelona and Milan, competition among initiatives for food donations, funds and skills is a barrier, which limits the cooperation and the building of solid networks with similar objectives. Interviewees from these two cities report some frictions among operators which have to work together (BCN 3.4.2.10; MIL 3.7.3, 3.10). In Barcelona FSIs are not fully vertically integrated and the different sizes, objectives and professionalisation levels can lead to conflicts. More professionalised initiatives have difficulties to cooperate with small FSIs mainly based on volunteers (BCN 3.4.2.10). In Milan, administration plays the role of facilitators which enables coordination among the different actors (MIL 3.10). In contrast, the governance landscape of Utrecht reports no conflict but a cooperation among different initiatives, which usually share spaces in the municipal community centres (UTH 4.3.2). The differences between Milan and Barcelona as opposed to Utrecht are likely attributed to the number of FSIs in each city. Barcelona and Milan have numerous small initiatives and a few prominent initiatives with strong organizational structures, along with a substantial number of professionalized volunteers. In Utrecht, there are fewer FSIs, and volunteering appears to be more organized compared to Italy and Spain.

The three governance landscape reports agree on the constructive relationships between initiatives and the municipal administrations, which, besides offering resources, spaces, and funds to the sector, facilitates the organisation of the food redistribution (BCN 3.4.1.5; UTH 4.3.4; MIL 3.6.2, 3.6.4). Indeed, the coordinator role of the City Councils is a crucial enabler recognised in all the three hubs. However, initiatives in Utrecht perceive this position as overwhelming and a factor of possible tensions (UTH 4.5.2).

The collaborations between the private sector and FSIs is recognised as a decisive enabler in Utrecht only, where interviewees highlights the constructive link built with one-time or regular donations with shops (UTH 4.3.3). However, there seems to be a tension regarding trust and agency in the partnerships, especially for less formal activities (e.g. dumpster diving) and food storing (UTH 4.5.1). Conversely, both Milan and Barcelona report difficulties in collaborating directly with the private sector. In Barcelona, shops and grocery stores are sometimes unwilling to cooperate with initiatives and the public administration (BCN 3.4.2.9). In Milan, supermarkets and grocery stores tend to prefer collaborating with the most "professionalised" initiatives, thereby limiting cooperation with smaller ones (MIL 3.7.3). The role of the administration tends to mediate these tensions through the hubs (MIL 3.6.2), but the collection of food surplus is mainly organised through agreements between FSIs and private actors without a standard framework (MIL 3.10).

3.2 Community-based Urban Agriculture

3.2.1 Structural Factors, Local Conditions and Discourses

The three hubs' sociocultural and economic dynamics appear to be the fertile ground for developing community-based urban agriculture initiatives (*aka* food sharing gardens in this report). Interviewees' answers and the analysis of academic and grey literature seem to depict the three hub cities as places where community initiatives, agriculture – also in its collective forms – and hospitality are significant features of the local history and cultural values. Historically, the three cities have been production centres and the pivotal distribution point of complex food systems. In recent decades, however, urban agriculture initiatives have experienced a decline as primary centers for urban food production and geared towards becoming places to improve social interaction and cohesion (UTH 3.7.1; BCN 2.6.1; MIL 2.5.1). Milan, Utrecht, and Barcelona have historically attracted national and international immigrants thanks to their dynamic economy and industrialisation, creating a hospitality culture. Urban agriculture is also part of the local history of the three cities. In particular, Utrecht reports that collective urban agriculture is part of a historic Dutch tradition (UTH 3.4.5). The analysis reveals that the sociocultural background is a crucial enabler for CBUA in all three cities. Barcelona and Milan have a relevant history of associationism and cooperativism, and Utrecht has a sharing and participatory culture visible in local planning (UTH 3.7.1; BCN 2.6.1; MIL 2.5.1).

Milan and Utrecht have a similar situation concerning the environmental aspects shaping this activity. They lie in flat lands rich in water, which have been historically managed to be intensive productive landscapes (UTH 3.7.1; MIL 2.5.1). In Milan, there are 1700ha of agricultural fields, of which 800 are owned by the City Council (MIL 2.1). Utrecht manages 1720 ha of green areas (UTH 3.1.1). In contrast, the complex orography, dense urban fabric, and low water availability are significant barriers in Barcelona. In addition, the city is dealing with periodic droughts due to climate change. This pushes local administrations to set water restrictions, which inevitably affect the development of urban agriculture (BCN 2.6.3).

The political and public discourses act as enablers for CBUA initiatives, as environmental and social sustainability has been at the centre of the public debate in the three hub cities. During the last decade, left, centre-left and green parties have ruled the three municipalities in Barcelona, Milan and Utrecht, respectively, whose agendas focused on increasing and enhancing green areas, as well as improving urban agriculture's role. Indeed, community-based urban agriculture initiatives have increased in number, participants, and spaces in the same period (UTH 3.7.2; BCN 2.6.2; MIL 2.5.2). This increase shows a growing collective interest in the intersection between urban agriculture and community action by many organisations that goes beyond the political discourse *per se*. In addition, the three municipal administrations have created specialised offices and departments to manage and actively improve these initiatives.

3.2.2 Regulatory and Policy Frameworks

The three cities have developed regulatory frameworks for community-based urban agriculture that mainly represent enablers for these initiatives. The common aspect that emerges from the documents is the social function – integration and cohesion – these initiatives assume (BCN 2.2.1; UTH 3.4.3; MIL 2.2.1). The documents address funds and resources (i.e. water supply and technical

staff), regulate the settlement of new initiatives, the accessibility to the allotments and their management, and crop distribution.

The scenario differs among the three cities regarding integrating urban agriculture into other policies, frameworks, and departments. Utrecht urban planning supports urban agriculture by creating new public spaces, especially for bottom-up initiatives. Despite the policy fragmentation and lack of specific policies on food or urban agriculture, Utrecht is making an effort to integrate approaches and collaborate across municipal departments, mainly when projects include different objectives (UTH 3.4.4). However, the integration among other policies and departments is limited to specific projects (UTH 3.4.2, 3.5.2). In the case of , Barcelona, the city council includes urban agriculture initiatives in its urban planning with a strategic approach that privileges community initiatives (BCN 2.5.1.1). Nevertheless, interviewees report limited coordination among the different areas of the City Council, which creates conflicts and competition. In contrast, the scenario of Milan seems to have many barriers in this aspect. The Urban Plan of Milan considers community gardens and urban agriculture as general green areas, and no specific programmes have been integrated for the following years (MIL 2.4.2). The Education Department is the only department directly involved in educational urban gardens in schools. The Urban Agriculture Unity, part of the Food Policy Office, only works with initiatives hosted in the fields owned by the municipality (MIL 2.4.2). Indeed, urban gardens and horticulture settlements are in charge of the 9 Municipalities - these submunicipal administrations manage the assignation processes and the maintenance tasks (MIL 2.2.2.4).

The interviewees from the three cities report a lack of coherence and political ambition that actually limits the improvement of food sharing gardens. In Utrecht, the policy fragmentation causes a complex bureaucracy that limits access to funds and support (UTH 3.5.1). In Barcelona and Milan, the lack of coordination among departments causes uncertainty and difficulties in working with the administrations (BCN 2.5.2.8, MIL 2.4.2). In addition, interviewees from Barcelona report the lack of regulation for the roof gardens regarding selling products and creating new initiatives (BCN 2.5.2.10).

Moreover, interviewees from Barcelona and Milan report two other barriers related to the regulatory frameworks: the selling ban on the food produced in community gardens and the limited access to allotments in public community gardens, respectively. Products must be for self-consumption and cannot be sold to third parties – Milan even forbids redistribution. Barcelona also forbids redistribution, but local authorities' leniency allows such activity. (BCN 2.5.2.9; MIL 2.4.6). This restriction can limit innovation and the development of more organised initiatives. Only social enterprises and cooperatives can sell their product and reinvest benefits in their activities (MIL 2.4.6). However, initiatives in Barcelona report a lack of enforcement of food safety regulations, which is actually an enabler for them and a benefit for redistribution initiatives. Food surplus from community gardens is donated to local associations, giving vulnerable people fresh and organic food (BCN 2.5.1.3). In addition, the regulatory framework on animal agriculture is reported as a barrier to innovation and the creation of new initiatives in Utrecht. Except for educational purposes, urban farming is subjected to the same standards as private companies (UTH 3.5.7).

Concerning access limitations, the scarcity of land pushes temporal urban gardens, which impede long-term planning in Barcelona. Indeed, the local administration prioritises community initiatives

rather than individual ones (BCN 2.5.2.1). The regulatory framework Milan assigns lots for a limited period and privileges elderly and low-income citizens, limiting access to new initiatives and participants (MIL 2.4.1). In contrast, Utrecht is promoting urban agriculture through its spatial development strategy, which allows the creation of these initiatives in any public space if public access to the areas is guaranteed (UTH 3.4.2).

3.2.3 Resources and Knowledge

3.2.3.1 Funding schemes

The three reports on the Governance Landscapes agree on the availability of funds devoted to food sharing gardens and urban agriculture in general. Public or private entities (e.g. foundations) offer FSIs the opportunity to cover at least the initial costs, which, as interviewees report, represent the most expensive step of these initiatives. FSIs in Barcelona and Utrecht can rely on municipal funds devoted to building urban gardens (i.e. fencing, ground preparation, and water supply connection) and the support of experts. In contrast, The City of Milan does not provide any direct funding option – Regione Lombardia (the regional administration) is the only public entity that funds educational, therapeutic, and community gardens. Especially in Milan and Barcelona, the private sector also plays a role in funding urban food sharing gardens and agriculture, which helps FSIs through sponsorships, donations and foundations' funds (La Caixa Foundation and Fondazione Cariplo) (BCN 2.5.1.2, 2.5.2.2; UTH 3.4.1; MIL 2.3.3; 2.4.4). In contrast, interviewees from Utrecht report a monopolisation of the public administration in the funding scheme, which is considered a barrier to innovation and the development of new initiatives (UTH. 3.5.3).

3.2.3.2 Spaces, Soil Conditions and Other Resources

Space availability has emerged, with different focuses, as a crucial barrier to developing food-sharing gardens in all three hubs. Barcelona has a structural lack of areas for urban agriculture and urban food sharing gardens due to its orography and dense urban fabric (BCN 2.5.2.4). Land access is limited, and urban agriculture competes with other social facilities for space (e.g., schools and social centres) (BCN 2.5.2.1). The other two hubs have better geographic conditions for agriculture, but few spaces are devoted to FSIs. In Utrecht, urban agriculture competes with the need for spaces for housing and other public service facilities (UTH 3.6.1). Although the City of Milan owns about 800 ha of agricultural fields, only 2.22% of them are devoted to community-based urban agriculture. In addition, public allotments for community gardens are not enough, considering the high demand and the regulatory framework which privileges fragile populations (see 3.2.2)

Contaminated soils are a further barrier for FSIs – they limit the opportunity to build edible gardens for self-consumption. Barcelona, Milan and Utrecht have hosted heavy and chemical industries for decades that have left many brownfields in which decontamination and conversion to agriculture would incur excessive costs for the FSIs and the administrations themselves. When facing contaminated soils, initiatives opted for boxed or table vegetable gardens, increasing the initial costs (BCN 2.5.2.3; UTH 2.3.2.2; MIL 2.4.3).

3.2.3.3 Technical Knowledge and Skills

The presence of staff in the public administration devoted to urban agriculture and food sharing gardens is recognised as a relevant enabler in Barcelona and Utrecht. The City Council provides technical staff who help participants organise their activities, and develop and assess the feasibility

of new initiatives. In Barcelona, the administration provides or hires through tenders technical staff who guide and monitor participants in their daily tasks (BCN 2.5.1.4). In Utrecht, Utrecht Natuurlijk is a crucial organisation that, besides managing the municipal farms and gardens, works as a knowledge hub to advise and share skills with residents, and support the creation of new urban agriculture initiatives (UTH 3.4.6). In contrast, Milan's City Council lacks specialised technical and organisational support, which is recognised as a barrier to urban agriculture and food sharing garden initiatives. Its intervention is limited to the management level: the allotment assignment and maintenance and the urban agriculture activities on the fields the city owns. An initial technical supervision is provided for educational gardens in schools only (MIL 2.2.2.4; 2.4.2).

3.2.4 Participation and Internal Organisation

3.2.4.1 Volunteering, Individual Culture and Possible Conflicts

In all three cities, interviewees recognise a high participation level, which is also considered a crucial enabler. Utrecht, Milan and Barcelona report that the waiting lists for allotments and the number of bottom-up initiatives show a high general interest in urban agriculture initiatives (BCN 2.2.1.5, 2.2.1.6; UTH 3.4.5; MIL 2.4.1, 2.2.2). In this direction, associations and bottom-up initiatives play significant roles in attracting new participants and sharing knowledge on urban agriculture (BCN 2.5.1.5; UTH 3.4.6; MIL 2.2.2.8). In Barcelona, interviewees recognise as an enabler the 'flexible participation' in urban gardens – there are different degrees of involvement in some food sharing gardens, meaning that participants help each other and work on the gardens according to their availability and resources (BCN 2.5.1.5; UTH 3.4.6).

Nevertheless, sometimes opposing visions and leaderships can emerge and they could represent a barrier, since they increase the possibility of internal conflicts (BCN 2.5.3; UTH 3.6). In addition, the 'individualised culture' emerges as a relevant barrier when analysing Milan and Barcelona, which contrasts the community dynamics and projects. In these two cities, interviewees report experiences of participants prioritising individual interests over the community interests, when, for example, at the harvesting stage, some participants can appropriate the harvest for themselves, rather than share it with all the gardeners and/or other organisations. This phenomenon causes overwork and over-responsibility for the most active participants. It also makes the organisation of maintenance and management tasks unclear, resulting in possible internal conflicts (BCN 2.5.2.6; MIL 2.4.5). In addition, Barcelona reports a lack of facilitators to help the community work together. Such a role is crucial and sometimes assumed by the City Council's technical staff (BCN 2.5.2.5). Interviewees in Utrecht see, as a potential barrier, relying on volunteers only because participation levels fluctuate over time and among the initiatives. There are different participant loads among initiatives: some experience an overload of volunteers while others lack. Furthermore, Utrecht Natuurlijk reports that most volunteers cannot work independently, requiring the guidance of the technical staff (UTH 3.5.6).

3.2.4.2 Networks and Conflicts among Actors

Interviewees from the three hubs agree that local networks are crucial enablers but report a complex scenario where conflicts and collaborations coexist. Indeed, urban agriculture initiatives compete for space and funds and, at the same time, work together to share skills, knowledge and even spaces (BCN 2.5.3, 2.5.1.3; UTH 3.4.6, 3.6.1; MIL 2.3.2). In addition, the collaboration with

other food sharing initiatives (e.g. redistribution and cooking FSIs) is recognised as an enabler that creates synergies. For example, some urban gardens in Barcelona give food surplus to charity organisations (BCN 2.5.1.3). In Milan, some collaborate with environmental associations and other initiatives or social enterprises devoted to job integration and social inclusion (MIL 2.2.2.8).

Interviewees from Barcelona and Utrecht mainly see the current relationships with public administrations as enablers. These administrations play crucial roles; they provide direct technical support and funds (BCN 2.5.1.2, 2.5.1.4; UTH 3.4.1, 3.4.2, 3.4.6). In addition, Utrecht's interviewees recognise collaboration among the different municipal departments as an enabler (UTH 3.4.4). However, initiatives in Utrecht report a potential conflict due to the regulatory and policy frameworks. In particular, the administrations prioritise and push community experiences rather than individual horticultural allotments (UTH 3.6.2), and for Barcelona, the selling ban is seen as a conflict point and a barrier (BCN 2.5.2.9, 2.5.3). In contrast, the involvement of the City Council of Milan in urban agriculture and food sharing garden initiatives is limited to the management of the allotments, which is, in turn, delegated to the submunicipal administrations (see 3.2.2). This minimal intervention is a barrier that indirectly encourages individual horticultural activities (MIL 2.4.2).

In the three cities, the relationships between urban agriculture initiatives and the private sector are minimal in urban agriculture and food sharing gardens, and this aspect can be considered a barrier even if not explicitly reported. Indeed, a common recommendation highlighted in the following chapter is better private sector involvement in urban agriculture. These collaborations are highlighted only in Barcelona and Milan. The interviews from Utrecht only mention that private urban agriculture initiatives work as businesses and have relationships with their collateral activities (e.g. initiatives that combine urban agriculture and restaurant or catering) (UTH 3.2). In Milan, the relationships with the private sector are primarily sponsorships that provide materials and tools in educational gardens and, in some cases, space in private premises (MIL 2.2.2.2, 2.2.2.3). Similarly, the relationship with the private sector in Barcelona is limited to urban gardens in private premises with free or rent agreements (BCN 2.6.2).

4. Recommendations Emerged in the Three City Hubs

4.1 Food Recovery and Redistribution

4.1.1 For Administrations and Policymakers

The general recommendations that emerged from the three governance landscape reports for the public sector are the most numerous and detailed and are summarised in Table 2 (BCN 3.6.1; UTH 4.6.1; MIL 3.12.1). Administrations and policymakers should consider the needs in terms of resources required by the initiatives. As mentioned above (see 3.1.3.2), food recovery and redistribution require economic efforts and suitable spaces for guaranteeing food security. Public administrations are recommended to increase funds, technical support, and space for the initiatives, which primarily rely on these channels of resources. In particular, small and new initiatives require significant support from the local administrations. More public sector involvement is also recommended in food surplus management and storage and in facilitating the collaboration of private donors, which is currently limited to supermarkets. Administrations should enlarge with ad hoc policies, strategies and actions the recovery activity to all the food-related companies (from agrifood to small grocery shops or canteens). Moreover, micro-actions are also recommended, such as providing community fridges in public premises.

Concerning the local level, the public sector in Barcelona should apply the regional law on Food Loss and Waste Prevention and, similarly to Utrecht, define and share clear guidelines and organise training paths for a safe redistribution of the food surplus. Utrecht needs specific funds for these initiatives and new ways to share food surplus to remove the social stigma. Finally, according to the analysis, the municipal administration of Milan should create a shared and comprehensive data system to gather data and monitor food redistribution activities.

4.1.2 For Food Sharing Initiatives

Concerning the recommendations for the initiatives (Table 3) (BCN 3.6.2; UTH 4.6.2; MIL 3.12.2), the three governance landscape analysis agree on improving the dialogue among similar and other FSIs and building networks to share skills, knowledge, spaces, and funds. The creation of networks may help overcome competition for funds and resources and have more significant political weight when collaborating with the public and private sectors.

In particular, initiatives in Barcelona are recommended to foster collaboration with the scientific sector and technical entities from the private and public sectors to improve logistics and technical challenges. Recommendations to FSIs in Milan focus on improving participation and local presence, such as creating a better and alternative approach to recruiting volunteers and enhancing communication regarding their activities and roles for the local community.

4.1.3 For the Private Sector

The recommendations for the private sector summarised in Table 4 (BCN 3.6.3; UTH 4.6.3; MIL 3.12.3) focus on a more significant commitment to food surplus recovery. In particular, the three governance landscape reports stress complying with the national and local policies, strategies and

incentives on food waste reduction and surplus redistribution, creating direct collaborations and networks with FSIs and improving the communication of their actions on this topic.

At the local level, the private sector in Barcelona should increase the employees' awareness of food loss and waste issues and the right to food through internal communication campaigns and purposefully designed activities. In contrast, the recommendation for private initiatives in Milan focuses on organising the food surplus donation, such as creating a standard policy to coordinate food donation (e.g. similar expiration date, efficiency to waste reduction, and food typology) and harmonising the dialogue with FSIs and local administrations.

RECOMMENDATIONS on FOOD WASTE RECOVER & REDISTRIBUTION

PUBLIC SECTOR

<p>GENERAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More support to food recovery and redistribution initiatives, especially those in the initial phases. • Provide more stable and long-term subsidies to food redistribution initiatives. • Improve and enlarge the contribution of food-related companies, not only for supermarkets with benefits and awareness. • Increase the role of the public administration in food surplus management and storage. • Long-term and structural funds. • Community fridges for every neighbourhood. 	<p>BARCELONA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply the Lay 03/2020 of Food Loss and Waste prevention by encouraging agrifood companies. • Set and define guidelines for the safe redistribution of food surpluses.
	<p>UTRECHT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funds for bottom-up initiatives
	<p>MILAN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a comprehensive and capillary data system that gathers information from different sectors and places. • Design a private donor fundraising scheme to support the entire sector.

Table 2 - Recommendations on urban food sharing gardens for the public sector. In orange, the recommendations emerged from the discussion at the CULTIVATE General Assembly, Utrecht - 15th-16th May 2024.

RECOMMENDATIONS on FOOD WASTE RECOVER & REDISTRIBUTION

FSIs

<p>GENERAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the dialogue with other FSIs and create networks. • Improve the collaboration with the private sector and local producers. • Overcome competition for joint efforts in applying funds and reaching resources. • Education of FSIs on food safety legislation needs to be improved to prevent unnecessary food waste. 	<p>BARCELONA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster collaborations with scientific and technical organisations to address the existing technical and logistical challenges.
	<p>UTRECHT</p>
	<p>MILAN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create an alternative approach to volunteer recruitment. • Improve communication and local presence.

Table 3 – Recommendations on food waste recover and redistribution for the Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs). In orange, the recommendations emerged from the discussion at the CULTIVATE General Assembly, Utrecht - 15th-16th May 2024

RECOMMENDATIONS on FOOD WASTE RECOVER & REDISTRIBUTION

PRIVATE SECTOR

<p>GENERAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comply with National and local incentives and policies on food waste reduction. • Create more strict collaborations and networks with FSIs. • Improve communication on actions taken in FWR. 	<p>BARCELONA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster awareness among their employees on the food loss and waste problem and the right to food.
	<p>UTRECHT</p>
	<p>MILAN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a common policy to coordinate food donation (i.e., similar expiration date, efficiency to waste reduction, and food typology). • Harmonize the dialogue with non-profit organizations and administrations.

Table 4 – Recommendations on food waste recover and redistribution for the private sector. In orange, the recommendations emerged from the discussion at the CULTIVATE General Assembly, Utrecht - 15th-16th May 2024.

4.2 Food Sharing Gardens and Urban Agriculture

4.2.1 For Administrations and Policymakers

The general recommendations for the public sector are summarised in Table 5 (BCN 2.8.1; UTH 3.9.1; MIL 2.6.1). The analysis of enablers and barriers reveals that food sharing gardens and urban agriculture initiatives rely mainly on public sector intervention and support (see 3.2). Indeed, recommendations for this sector focus on increasing the resources addressed to urban agriculture and food sharing gardens: public funds and budget, areas, technical support and supplies, and tools. Moreover, creating guidelines and training paths for improving technical skills and knowledge of the funding schemes and bureaucracy is further significant advice for public entities. From the administrative and strategic sides, recommendations focus on integrating these initiatives in urban planning by developing specific plans and policies, participatory approaches, and improving coordination among the different municipal departments. In addition, the public sector should study the opportunity offered by allowing for the commercialisation of food cultivated in urban gardens, and facilitate and push the engagement of the private sector, whose involvement is currently marginal in urban agriculture initiatives, as it may promote innovation and improvements in these practices.

Barcelona and Milan have similar recommendations at the city level: better advocacy structure and organisation for food sharing gardens, creating communication and knowledge-sharing platforms for participants and gathering information, and finding solutions for soil contamination. In this direction, recommendations for Utrecht focus on developing plans to ensure social sustainability and a coherent approach with defined long-term objectives. In addition, Barcelona and Utrecht are in line to request a review of the regulatory documents on food safety and small-scale animal agriculture, respectively. Milan and Barcelona analysis reveals the need for the public sector to develop a strategic vision which includes better support and higher levels of involvement. Recommendations for Utrecht focus instead on improving the existing involvement of the local administration and Utrecht Natuurlijk.

4.2.2 For Food Sharing Initiatives

Recommendations for FSIs mainly focus on participation and internal organisation in the three cities (BCN 2.8.2; UTH 3.9.2; MIL 2.6.2) (Table 6). In particular, they ask for increasing the accessibility of new members and, simultaneously, setting clear rules and tools (e.g., guidelines) and social pacts to reduce the risk of internal conflicts. This aspect reveals the organisational issues experienced by some bottom-up initiatives when the number of participants increases. In addition, networking and education are crucial recommendations, highlighting the need to create more solid collaborations with the third and private sectors. Sharing skills and knowledge within the community and with other initiatives through events and better communication is suggested as a driver to increase participation and attract new members.

At the local level, the analysis includes Barcelona and Utrecht addressing specific recommendations according to their governance landscapes. Recommendations for Barcelona focus on the internal organisation of initiatives. Results suggest developing a system of sharing and increasing internal structural transparency. These recommendations show the organisational issues and weaknesses of

bottom-up initiatives concerning their organisation. Besides ensuring a socially sustainable engagement and stable participation, the recommendations for FSIs in Utrecht focus on improving collaboration with the existing networks and with the private sector. This focus reveals the preponderant role the public sector plays in these initiatives.

4.2.3 For the Private Sector

Recommendations for the private sector are similar for the three hub cities (BCN 2.8.3; UTH 3.9.1; MIL 2.6.1), and no further recommendations were made during the General Assembly (Table 7). Recommendations focus on more private sector engagement in urban agriculture initiatives and food sharing gardens, providing economic support and spaces for these initiatives on their premises, and being involved in networks and associations devoted to urban agriculture. In all three cities, initiatives recognise the relevant role the private sector may play in driving innovative practices thanks to their economic and space resources.

RECOMMENDATIONS on COMMUNITY-BASED URBAN AGRICULTURE

PUBLIC SECTOR

GENERAL	BARCELONA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase available funding and resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase budgets for urban gardening in the City Council ○ Create guidelines for community gardens with potential funding sources. ○ Facilitate additional resources (electricity, matter for compost) ○ Systematise the process of facilitating access to gardening materials and services (e.g., create official and accessible online forms to request electricity, wood chipper, carbon-rich material for compost making, etc.) ● Include urban agriculture in urban planning and policies. ● Consider gardens as municipal facilities. ● Increase access and spaces for urban agriculture. ● Create specific programmes for urban food sharing gardens. ● Increase coordination among City Councils' Departments. ● Facilitate the engagement of the private sector with food sharing gardens. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enforce urban garden guidelines. ● Adapt to the climate emergency (e.g., create shades and water catcher systems). ● Find better ways to decontaminate soils. ● Create an advocacy structure for Community Gardens. ● Create a public platform for centralising all information and communicating about community gardens. ● Review food safety regulations to include exceptions for donations of freshly produced vegetables. ● Soil analysis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Study possible commercialisation opportunities for products. ● Create participatory projects for urban gardening. ● Engage people in planning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Centre an approach to UA by creating a coherent policy with clearly defined ambitions. ● Find a balance between stability and monopolisation of the sector. ● Create a legislative framework for small-scale animal agriculture in the city. ● Develop a plan for the management and governance of Rijnvliet ensuring long-term social sustainability. ● Develop shared maintenance plans.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Push the involvement of the private sector (directly related to agriculture and not) and landlords. ● Facilitate soil remediation and analysis. ● Create an advocacy structure for urban food sharing gardens. ● Create a public platform for centralising all information and communicating about gardens and participants.

Table 5 - Recommendations on urban food sharing gardens for the public sector. In orange, the recommendations emerged from the discussion at the CULTIVATE General Assembly, Utrecht - 15th-16th May 2024.

RECOMMENDATIONS on COMMUNITY-BASED URBAN AGRICULTURE

FSIs

<p>GENERAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase participation and accessibility to the FSIs. • Promote facilitation tools among participants. • Sharing skills, resources and funds. • Creating networks also with the private sector to increase the political weight. • Improve communication with events and activities. • Create “How to solve conflicts” guidelines. • Clear rules. • Social pacts. • Educational activities. 	<p>BARCELONA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System of sharing. • Social transparent structure.
	<p>UTRECHT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find ways to engage with the private sector for financial (and other) collaborations. • Engage in the existing networks, such as BuurtNatuur030. • Promote socially sustainable engagement and stable participation.
	<p>MILAN</p>

Table 6 – Recommendations on urban food sharing gardens for the Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs). In orange, the recommendations emerged from the discussion at the CULTIVATE General Assembly, Utrecht - 15th-16th May 2024

RECOMMENDATIONS on COMMUNITY-BASED URBAN AGRICULTURE

PRIVATE SECTOR

<p>GENERAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider funding community-based urban agriculture. • Create food sharing gardens on private premises. • Create or be members of networks with other organisations to manage food-sharing gardens located on private and public premises. 	<p>BARCELONA</p>
	<p>UTRECHT</p>
	<p>MILAN</p>

Table 7 – Recommendations on urban food sharing gardens for the private sector. In orange, the recommendations emerged from the discussion at the CULTIVATE General Assembly, Utrecht - 15th-16th May 2024

5. Conclusions

The landscape governance analysis comparison has revealed that despite differing socio-demographic and environmental conditions, the three hub cities share similar enablers and barriers for furthering the sustainability and impact of FSI. Furthermore, similarities and differences between community-based urban agriculture and food waste recovery and redistribution initiatives have also been observed. The comparison of recommendations across the public, FSIs, and private sectors, as well as cities, has provided insights into the varying and common needs of FSIs initiatives and the roles that the public and private sectors, along with FSIs, should undertake in the coming years.

The sociocultural fabric of all three cities provides fertile ground for food sharing initiatives that focus on urban agriculture and the recovery and redistribution of food waste. Barcelona, Utrecht, and Milan boast a rich history of solidarity, cooperation, and associationism, which is closely tied to their robust economies, the strength of their social movements, and their ability to attract new residents (3.1.1, 3.2.1). Additionally, there is a widespread recognition in the political discourse and public opinion that access to sustainable food is essential for the well-being of the community. While the political agenda has increasingly focused on these issues in recent decades, food sharing initiatives consider that more can be done and have outlined recommendations in this direction for improvement (4.1, 4.2).

Concerning the regulatory and policy frameworks, the governance landscape analyses coincide on highlighting that food sharing and related topics should be included in various planning activities as a cross-cutting issue. However, dividing the topic could create organizational and administrative challenges within the public sector and uncertainty for FSIs and the private sector (3.1.2, 3.2.2). From this perspective, the case of Utrecht serves as a clear example (UTH 3.5.1, 4.4.2). Having overarching strategies and policies appears to facilitate administrative action and dialogue between FSIs and the public and private sectors. Moreover, having clear rules, protocols, and procedures is a crucial facilitator for FSIs, especially those addressing food security. In this context, public administrations should provide technical and bureaucratic support to FSIs and the private sector through training programs and guidelines (3.1.3.3, 3.2.3.3). Similarly, the governance landscape analyses report difficulties in accessing funds due to complex bureaucratic procedures for application and management (4.1.1, 4.2.1).

The lack of resources and funds are the most pressing barriers for CBUA and FWR in the three cities. All interviewees emphasise the need for more and better physical spaces for their activities, particularly for FWR, and an increase in economic support from the public sector (3.2.3, 3.1.3). Recommendations for administrations and policymakers underline this necessity (4.1.1, 4.2.1). The needs of CBUA initiatives are centered on expanding areas dedicated to urban agriculture, including green spaces and locations for boxed gardens (3.2.3.2). Technical and bureaucratic skills are critical enablers, especially for FWR initiatives that require support in navigating complex collection protocols and regulatory frameworks for food recovery, as well as in the management and application processes for funds (3.1.1).

Participation plays a crucial role for FSIs. Although the number of volunteers has generally increased in the last decade in the three cities, there are dynamics that can negatively influence the internal

organization, activities, and external relationships (3.1.4.1, 3.2.4.1). FWR and CBUA initiatives have different forms of participation. Food recovery and redistribution require close collaboration among volunteers, while urban agriculture is more inclined to individualistic behaviours. The reports indicate the existence of two levels of involvement: groups or individuals deeply involved in their initiatives, who may or may not hold leadership positions, and other volunteers who have sporadic participation or individualistic behaviours. Leading volunteers are the most 'professionalised' and provide stability to FSIs through their efforts and experience in navigating bureaucratic and funding processes. However, this may lead to overwork for these professionalized volunteers and internal conflicts regarding the organization, objectives, and visions. Indeed, recommendations for FSIs focus on participation, reducing internal conflicts, increasing participation, and establishing clear rules for new members (4.1.2, 4.2.2).

Across the three governance landscapes, it is evident that creating networks among similar and diverse initiatives, at different scales and in various sectors, is a crucial factor. This facilitates stronger dialogues with the public and private sectors, reduces competition for resources in favor of collaboration, and enhances local presence through effective communication and events. When it comes to relationships with the private and public sectors, there is consensus across the three governance landscapes about the significant and potentially improving role they play. Administrations should foster dialogues and create the necessary conditions for these initiatives. The private sector, whether connected to food or not, should establish constructive dialogues with the FSIs and become more involved in food sharing activities (4.1.2, 4.1.3, 4.2.1, 4.2.3). Notwithstanding, it is important to consider the diversity of actors and initiatives under the private sector banner and identify which ways of engagement can be more fruitful to include in these transformations small and medium enterprises, as well as local and independent businesses.

In a broader context, the governance landscapes indicate that the administration of Milan primarily focuses on food waste recovery and redistribution rather than urban agriculture. In contrast, the public sector in Utrecht places greater emphasis on food sharing gardens. The Barcelona City Council appears to be equally involved in both types of initiatives.

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